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SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND ETHICAL ISSUES IN COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

The behavior of companies in Brazil can both solidify the brand, but also demoralize it, which is why it is fundamental to the organization's success, especially when it comes to administration, where values and ethical issues can go beyond the issue of "profit", and in this sense, by involving external factors that years ago were not even questioned. The involvement of companies with the scenario that surrounds them can define morally questionable issues that today have value and can define the brand value of a company. Behavior can go beyond environmental issues, and in this sense encompass discussions of ethics, respect, and social value. In this scenario, the ability to make effective decisions is fundamental to the success and survival of organizations. By adopting an ethical stance, companies strengthen their reputation and build a relationship of trust with stakeholders, which can result in benefits. Therefore, by understanding the most sustainable practices, companies can quantify and manage ways to overcome and improve their performance.

KEYWORDS : Behavior; Brand; Factors; Value; Improvement.

INTRODUCTION

Humans' remarkable ability to adapt cannot be denied, not only to survive but to thrive in various natural environments. Throughout history, humanity has consistently demonstrated its resourcefulness in shaping the surrounding world to meet its needs for sustenance and comfort. This innate adaptability is evident in diverse environments, from facing the harsh conditions of deserts to navigating the challenges of tropical forests. However, a worrying observation emerges from this process: alteration of the natural environment often occurs without sufficient consideration, leading to unfavorable consequences. The increasing transformation of our surroundings coincides with the surprising growth of the population and a greater concentration of inhabitants in large metropolises.

According to Oliveira (2013), given the change that the Industrial Revolution provided for the expansion of markets, so that factories emerged that used machines that at the time were considered "modern", either through the steam process that made them more efficient and allowed mass production. In this sense, and highlighted by Oliveira, in addition to this revolution, a process of directly impacting mobility was initiated, whether due to the need for more agile logistics, with the construction of railways and other more advanced means of transport at the time.

However, according to Dias (2011), this incessant search for economic growth and production efficiency has had a significant price for the environment. As the author points out, the Industrial Revolution also marked the increase in the consumption of non-renewable energy sources, such as coal and oil, to power machines and boost production. This has led to serious environmental impacts, including air pollution and degradation of natural resources. The relationship between man and nature has been profoundly altered, with the rampant exploitation of natural resources and environmental degradation becoming a growing concern.

DEVELOPMENT

The complex relationship between companies, society and the environment is emphasized, highlighting the constant search for balance between economic and social development. In this sense, according to Dias (2013), the incessant search for profit can leave both positive and negative impacts in different areas. As Oliveira (2013) points out, the central point of this context is the Industrial Revolution of the 18th century, which brought economic growth, increased wealth and improved quality of life, at the same time that it generated significant social and environmental problems.

For Oliveira, the use of new technologies boosted productivity and demand, leading to migration from rural to urban areas in search of jobs in factories. This resulted in significant social changes in the countryside and the creation of an urban working class in the cities, accompanied by the emergence of labor movements and socialist movements.

Dias highlights the importance of understanding the history of the Industrial Revolution as a fundamental antecedent to addressing contemporary issues of sustainability and corporate responsibility, maintaining a focus on the balance between economic and social development.

The emergence and evolution of social responsibility in companies throughout history are highlighted. Since ancient civilizations, such as Greece and Rome, productive organizations needed government authorization and fulfilled obligations to protect the population from the harmful effects of their activities.

The initial milestone of the classical approach to corporate social responsibility is associated with the publication of the book "The Gospel of Wealth" by Carnegie (1901). In this sense, for Carnegie, philanthropy and collective well-being are based on paternalistic and Christian principles, highlighting charity and custody as fundamental values. These principles required that the more fortunate help the less fortunate

and that companies and wealthy people act as guardians of the money earned, using it for the benefit of society.

When mentioning Henry Ford, Marques and Filho (2012), they indicate that a successful businessman was already mentioned as a defender of social responsibility practices. According to the authors, Ford believed that profits should benefit the company, the workers and the community. However, its actions in this regard resulted in legal issues, as part of the dividends intended for shareholders would be used for improvements in production and benefits for employees, which was considered contrary to the interests of shareholders by the courts.

According to Barbieri and Cajazeira (2013), after the depression of 1929, there was a change in the perception of companies, which began to be questioned regarding their exclusive focus on profits. According to the authors, the American government imposed regulations and discussions arose about corporate social responsibility, resulting in the creation of articles related to this issue.

In the 1950s and 1960s, the principles of charity and trust, initially promoted by Carnegie (1901), found widespread acceptance in American business. Many companies recognized that “power brings responsibility”, and even those that did not adopt these principles realized the need to accept social responsibilities, whether by conviction or government imposition.

Considered the beginning of the modern era of social responsibility in companies. Bowen (1953) emphasized the moral duty of business managers to align their actions with the values and objectives of society. He saw companies as centers of power and decision-making whose actions impacted society in different aspects.

During the 1960s, the United States faced business criticism due to its involvement in the Vietnam War. This social discontent has stimulated studies and research on social responsibility, with many of them seeking to define the concept more precisely. Influential authors of the time such as Freeman

(2008) were a prominent proponent of this view. For Friedman, companies should not assume any social responsibility other than seeking profit, respecting the rules of the free market economy. He argued that the only social responsibility of companies was to use their resources to increase profits within the rules of the competitive game, without deception or fraud.

Fig.1, Comparison of behavioral models

Source: Sant’Anna, (2015).

The 1980s marked the linking of environmental issues to the corporate social responsibility movement and the emergence of the term “corporate social responsiveness”, which emphasizes the proactivity of companies in addressing social issues in an early and preventive manner.

Carroll (1979) established comprehensive models of social responsibility that incorporate four categories: economic, legal, ethical and discretionary, representing society’s basic expectations in relation to companies. These decades have witnessed a profound shift in the understanding of corporate social responsibility, with emerging philosophical debates and regulations culminating in comprehensive models that incorporate multiple dimensions of social responsibility.

Carroll (1979) proposed a four-category model to represent the various responsibilities that society expects companies to assume: economic, legal,

ethical and discretionary.

In addition, Garriga and Mele (2004) developed a model based on the hierarchy of companies' needs, similar to Maslow's pyramid, emphasizing that companies have criteria to be met, like people. Freeman (2008), highlighting the importance of considering all interested parties, not just shareholders, in business decisions. This approach expanded the company's responsibilities.

Such studies sought to examine the relationship between social responsibility and company profitability. Carroll (1991) revised his model, renaming the discretionary category to philanthropic responsibilities. Other authors operationalized the four-category model, highlighting the importance of economic responsibility as a priority. Wartick and Cochran (1985) developed a model of corporate social performance and highlighted the role of stakeholders in corporate social responsibility. This evolution reflected a broader understanding of corporate social responsibility, incorporating new actors and perspectives into discussions.

The 1990s were marked by significant changes in the political, economic and social areas, creating a scenario that put pressure on companies to become more involved with social issues. During this decade, several theories and concepts developed in the 1980s were reformulated to address environmental, ethical, social, economic and political issues.

With Wood (1991), by significantly contributing to corporate social responsibility by proposing a model for evaluating the social performance of organizations. Their model built on previous work, including that of Carroll (1979); Wartick and Cochran (1985). This model sought a more realistic definition of corporate social responsibility, considering social principles, processes and results. In this sense, Wood created three levels of responsibility for companies:

In Legitimacy, according to Wood, the company must avoid abusing its power and must be socially responsible, because, if it loses the trust of interested parties, it may lose its legitimacy. With Public Responsibility, the company is

responsible for the results related to its primary and secondary areas of involvement with society, without the obligation to solve all social problems, but also without exempting itself from resolving problems related to its operations.

Wood's discretionary management defined the role of the manager to meet the various responsibilities, and the way in which his choices could influence the company's social behavior. In a complementary way, Wood also highlighted related behaviors in the social context of companies, which are highlighted in the following: Environmental Assessment, which involves the analysis of the external environment, which is dynamic and influenced by several factors. Companies must adapt and respond to these environmental conditions.

Stakeholder Management refers to the company's ability to manage its relationship with interested parties, recognizing the importance of considering parties other than shareholders.

Problem Management, involving the development and monitoring of internal and external processes designed to manage the company's responses to social issues.

However, not only Wood proposed practices, but Almeida et al. (2012) by highlighting that social responsibility is not replaced by the Stakeholder concept, but would complement it by recognizing the importance of business understanding from the perspective of social responsibility.

From the 2000s onwards, theoretical discussions about Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) evolved into empirical research, addressing topics such as stakeholder theory, business ethics, sustainability and corporate citizenship (Werneck, 2013).

One of these models is two-dimensional, classifying companies along two axes: the first covers narrow responsibility, focused exclusively on maximizing profits, to broad responsibility, which involves community development and environmental preservation. The second axis considers the concern with the costs of CSR, focusing on short-term results, and the interest in the benefits of CSR, focusing on long-term

results.

According to Bicalho et al. (2003), also contributed by highlighting the domains of CSR: economic, legal and ethical, incorporating the philanthropic category into the ethical and/or economic domains. This model suggests that none of the three domains is more important than the other and allows for a more complete analysis of companies' activities in relation to CSR.

Garriga and Melé (2004) classified CSR theories and approaches into four groups: instrumental theories (aimed at improving the company's financial performance), political theories (concerned with the power of companies in society), integrative theories (where companies seek to integrate their actions with social demands) and ethical theories (based on ethical values and what is ethically correct).

Freeman's Stakeholder Theory (2008) brought new demands and opportunities to companies. In a study conducted by Boutilier and Ian Thomson (2012), the degree of support that companies receive from their stakeholders to conduct their activities was assessed. The authors highlight that stakeholders may have disagreements about what level of social license to operate (LSO) should be granted to a company, often due to political differences within the stakeholder network.

Ashley (2005) also observes that the concepts disseminated in Europe and the United States have cultural bases that are very different from the Brazilian reality. Despite the limitations to implementing social responsibility in Brazilian companies, it is possible to obtain satisfactory results.

According to Marques et al. (2012), the Brazilian Institute of Social and Economic Analysis (IBASE) was created, which encouraged companies to publish their social reports. In 1984, Nitrofértil, a Brazilian company in the chemical sector, published the country's first social report. In 1986, the Fundação Instituto de Desenvolvimento Empresarial e Social (FIDES) was created to integrate companies into society and promote the regular publication of social reports.

The Pensamento Nacional das Bases Empresariais

(PNBE) movement was created in 1987 by a group of young businesspeople from São Paulo who wanted to address social demands and the democratization of the country as part of sustainable development. This initiative inspired the creation of other business NGOs in Brazil, such as Fundação Abrinq, the São Paulo Institute against Violence, the Akatu Institute and Transparency International in Brazil.

According to Pereira et al. (2011), in 1995, the Group of Institutes, Foundations and Companies (GIFE) was created, the first entity in South America of private origin to finance and execute social, environmental and cultural projects of public interest. In 1977, Bill No. 3,116 made the publication of the social report mandatory for private companies with more than 100 employees and for all public companies, concessionaires and licensees of public services. The Securities and Exchange Commission (CVM) also started to require the inclusion of the social balance sheet in the financial statements of publicly traded companies.

In 1995, according to Marques et al. (2012), the Brazilian Institute of Corporate Governance (IBGC) was created by a group of businesspeople, executives and scholars to promote best corporate governance practices in Brazil. The Brazilian Business Council for Sustainable Development (CEBDS) was founded in 1997 by businesspeople who recognized the opportunities brought by sustainability from the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, Rio-92. The Ethos Institute for Business and Social Responsibility was created in 1998 to mediate the relationship between companies and social actions, promoting ethical and responsible practices in the business world.

Fig. 2, Development and Social responsibility

Source: Ebner and Baumgartner, (2008).

The Ethos Institute has developed a series of indicators to help companies incorporate social responsibility and sustainability into their business strategies. These indicators have become a reference for corporate social responsibility organizations in Latin America, and the Ethos Institute has worked in partnership with organizations in countries such as Argentina, Bolivia, Ecuador, Paraguay and Peru to adapt the indicators to local realities. In 1999, the Institute of Applied Economic Research (IPEA) carried out the first survey on social action by companies in Brazil, showing that 59% of companies carry out actions to benefit the community.

In 2009, the government of Minas Gerais launched the Business Responsibility Seal Program, in partnership with the State Secretariat for Development of the Jequitinhonha and Mucuri Valleys and the North of Minas (SEDVAN), the Institute for Development of the North and Northeast of Minas Gerais (IDENE) and the Minas Gerais Center for Intersectoral Alliances (CeMais). The program aims to recognize corporate responsibility actions by companies that promote social, economic and environmental development in the regions of Vales do Jequitinhonha, Mucuri and Norte de Minas, in Minas Gerais. Currently, the program has the participation of 80 companies that carry out 400 corporate responsibility initiatives in 24 municipalities within the program's coverage area. Companies that receive the seal can use it in their advertising campaigns, product packaging and promotional materials for two years, as long as they send monthly reports on their initiatives to the program to maintain the use of the seal. Business ethics plays a fundamental role in corporate social responsibility, focusing on company managers and the actions they take ethically. Understanding business ethics leads to the study of applied ethics, since companies are made up of individuals who make decisions and influence their behavior based on internalized norms and values. Ethics is one of the organizational cultural elements that contribute to the successful implementation of corporate social responsibility.

Business is based on ethical principles, and

companies must consider the collective construction of strategic interests. The legitimacy and credibility of a company depend on an ethical system of beliefs and values that is self-defined, assimilated and effectively fulfilled. The application of the concept of ethics in organizations is not only based on external pressures or government regulations, but on the desire to do the right thing. Ethics is the theory or science of the moral behavior of individuals in society and studies moral phenomena. Ethics and morals have common aspects, but ethics is the science of morals, and these terms are often used synonymously in everyday life.

Business ethics are fundamental to guide behavior and decisions in companies in accordance with ethical principles. The difference between ethics and morals is that ethics refers to the character and customs acquired or achieved by man, while morals relate to norms or rules acquired through habit. Scientific ethics provides concepts and guidelines that transcend ideological speculations and recognize the historical character of moralities. There are two predominant traditions in philosophy that distinguish between ethics and morals.

Aristotle argues that there are two types of virtues: intellectual virtue, which is acquired through teaching and experience over time, and moral virtue, which develops from habits and is not innate. This highlights the importance of the quality of the acts performed, as they will influence people's moral formation. Aristotle states that desire has "good" as its ultimate object, but for some people, this "good" is the true good, while for others, it is what appears to be good. The good man correctly evaluates things and desires the true good, while the bad man desires only the apparent good, often deluded by superficiality. The ability to correctly discern true good and make it a rule or measure distinguishes good people, and their actions reflect their choices.

According to Souza et al. (2011), the moral universe is multifaceted, with complex nuances, and does not always fit into simplistic dichotomies of right and wrong, hero and villain, light and darkness. For the authors, business ethics deals

with truth and justice in relation to various aspects, such as society's expectations, fair competition, advertising, social responsibility, consumption and business behavior at local and international levels. In this sense, Srour (2003) highlights that ethics in the business environment is fundamental, since business decisions have significant impacts and affect stakeholders, including employees, managers, owners, customers and suppliers, both internally and externally.

Three currents of ethical thought relevant to business decisions include virtue ethics and utilitarianism, both of which are considered teleological, and Kantian ethics, which is deontological. Each of these approaches offers different perspectives on morality in management practices and business decision-making.

Fig. 3, Business conduct according to Kantian ethics

1 - A empresa deve considerar os interesses de todos os stakeholders em todas as decisões que toma.
2 - Todos os afetados pelas regras e políticas da empresa devem poder participar na sua definição antes de serem implantadas.
3 - Nenhum stakeholder específico deve ser considerado automaticamente prioritário em todas as decisões da empresa.
4 - O número de indivíduos pertencentes a cada grupo de stakeholders não deve constituir critério suficiente que justifique a preferência pelos interesses de um grupo em detrimento de outro.
5 - Todas as empresas com fins lucrativos têm um dever genuíno, embora limitado, de beneficência perante a sociedade.

Source: (Bowie, 1999, apud Almeida, 2007, p.170).

According to Srour (2011), the dichotomy between ethical selfishness, which prioritizes personal benefit, and utilitarianism is present in discussions about ethics and corporate social responsibility. For the author, although personal interest is central in the capitalist market, market practices also involve risk, and the search for maximizing profits is a fundamental characteristic.

In the context of corporate responsibility, according to Soares (2002), it is essential to recognize two ethical approaches: the ethics of conviction and the ethics of responsibility, the ethics of conviction, based on firm personal beliefs, while the ethics of responsibility considers the consequences of actions for the community. In this sense, according to Werneck (2013), in order to qualify business leaders, the principles

of ethics and social responsibility must be emphasized. For the author, this requires a transformation in the curricula and pedagogical approaches of business schools. Educational institutions must collaborate with businesses to promote economic development, equality and social awareness.

Therefore, when observing what Werneck (2013); as Sour (2003-2011) highlights, this can contribute to the formation of managers committed to ethics, and being able to integrate corporate social responsibility into their practices.

CONCLUSION

The scenario that involves the paths surrounding corporate responsibility, in which related factors emerge today that go beyond the issue of ecological sustainability, but how organizations can review already established concepts and, in light of this, seek methods of understanding the issues that delimit each company and its own environment in which it operates.

For which, once the process of understanding has begun, and in this context, not only knowing its philosophy, but in order to visualize how and which methods and practices can be discussed in the face of factors that may flow from this process of "self-knowledge", whether not only delimited from the manager's perspective, but covering all actors that belong to the business environment.

However, it may be that it goes beyond the context of the "Industrial Revolution", and in this sense, today the technological process, even though it is not delimited in the article, can also enable new practices that come from the concepts that shape the responsibility of companies. In this sense, Sour (2003) already pointed out that the conversion of principles, whether in everyday practices, can form an ethical issue, so that companies analyze their practices and can review their beliefs, in order to reduce possible social impacts.

Therefore, by analyzing norms, forms, issues, and needs, organizations, not just large ones, but all, can define objectives and discuss alternatives.

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